

LEGAL REGULATION OF ADOPTION: A COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE
LEGISLATION OF UZBEKISTAN AND ENGLAND

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the legal regulation of adoption in Uzbekistan and England. A comparative legal analysis is provided of the legislation governing adoption, the requirements for adoptive parents, the rights and obligations of the parties, and the procedures for establishing and formalizing adoption. Based on this analysis, conclusions are drawn regarding areas for improving the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the area of adoption.

Keywords: adoption, adoptive parents, child, adoption procedure, children's interests, guardians, parents.

In today's world, adoption issues are particularly important, as they are directly linked to ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of children left without parental care. Effective legal regulation of adoption contributes to strengthening the institution of the family and the social protection of children. This institution has its own unique characteristics in different countries, conditioned by historical development, legal systems, and social traditions¹.

The relevance of the chosen topic is determined by the need to analyze and compare legislative norms regulating the adoption procedure in order to identify similarities and differences between the legal systems of Uzbekistan and England.

The purpose of this study is to conduct a comparative legal analysis of the adoption legislation of these countries. This will be achieved by examining the adoption process, requirements for adoptive parents, the rights and obligations of the parties, and identifying the specific legal frameworks in each country.

¹ Эсанова З. Н. Судебное рассмотрение дел об усыновлении в Узбекистане: дискуссии и предложения // Вестник Таджикского государственного университета права, бизнеса и политики. Серия гуманитарных наук. – 2009. – №. 1. – С. 33-40.

The object of this study is the institution of adoption as an element of family law, and the subject matter is the legislation of Uzbekistan and England regulating this institution. Comparative legal analysis is used as the primary research method.

Legal regulation of adoption procedures in the Republic of Uzbekistan is enshrined in the Family Code and the Civil Procedure Code. First, let's consider the cases in which adoption is permitted and the requirements for it². In accordance with Article 151 of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adoption is permitted only for minors and only in their interests. Adoption is carried out by the court upon the application of the person(s) wishing to adopt the child, taking into account the conclusion of the guardianship and trusteeship authorities on the validity and compliance of the adoption with the interests of the adopted child. Adoption cases are considered by the civil court in a special procedure according to the rules stipulated by the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with the participation of the adoptive parents (adoptive parent), representatives of the guardianship and trusteeship authorities, and the prosecutor³. It also states that the adoption of siblings by different persons is not permitted, except in cases where the adoption is in the best interests of the children. Article 152 of the Family Code states that adoptive parents may be adults of either sex. The following persons are not eligible to adopt:

- deprived of or limited in parental rights;
- recognized as incompetent or with limited legal capacity;
- registered in psychiatric or drug treatment facilities;
- former adoptive parents, if the adoption was canceled due to their fault;
- have a criminal record or a criminal case pending for serious, especially serious, or certain crimes against the individual, family, society, and the state, as provided for by the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- suffer from illnesses that prevent adoption. Another requirement is age⁴.

According to Part Two of Article 152 of this Code, the age difference between adoptive parents and adopted children must not be less than fifteen years, except in cases of adoption by stepparents or close relatives of the adoptee. If the child has reached the age of ten, the child's consent is required.

² Шарахметова У. Защита прав несовершеннолетних детей в международном частном праве // Обзор законодательства Узбекистана. – 2018. – №. 2. – С. 83-85.

³ АТАЛЫКОВА Г. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДОСУДЕБНЫЙ ЭТАПА И ВОЗБУЖДЕНИЕ ДЕЛ ОБ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ РЕБЕНКА //“XXI АСРДА ИЛМ-ФАН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ ВА УЛАРДА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ” МАВЗУСИДАГИ РЕСПУБЛИКА ИЛМИЙ-ONLINE КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯСИ МАТЕРИАЛЛАРИ. – С. 40.

⁴ Латипова Н. М. ВОПРОСЫ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ ДЕТЕЙ, ОСТАВШИХСЯ БЕЗ ПОПЕЧЕНИЯ РОДИТЕЛЕЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН // Современная гуманитарная наука: проблемы и перспективы развития. – 2015. – С. 193-197.

If the child is under ten, the consent of the child's parents, or the guardianship and trusteeship authority, or the administration of state children's institutions is required for adoption if the child is being raised and maintained by such an institution⁵. Adoption without parental consent occurs in cases where the parents are: unknown; deprived of parental rights; declared incompetent, missing, or deceased; or have not visited the child in a childcare or medical facility for more than one year without a valid reason. These circumstances determine the legal status of the child and the individuals who have no restrictions on adopting the child. Now let's look at the process itself, from the filing of the application to the court's decision.

The first step is filing an adoption application. According to Article 298 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an adoption application is submitted by citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan wishing to adopt a child to the inter-district, district (city) civil court at the place of residence (location) of the adopted child. Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan permanently residing outside the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign citizens, or stateless persons wishing to adopt a child who is a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan, submit an adoption application to the Court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional courts, or the Tashkent city court at the place of residence (location) of the adopted child. In accordance with Article 299 of this Code, the application must contain the following:

- the last name, first name, patronymic name of the adoptive parents (adoptive parent), and their (his) place of residence;
- the adopted child's last name, first name, patronymic, and date of birth, his or her place of residence (location), information about the adopted child's parents, and whether the child has siblings;
- circumstances justifying the adoptive parents' (adoptive parent's) request for adoption, and evidence confirming these circumstances;
- a request to change the adopted child's last name, first name, and patronymic, date of birth (by no more than one year), place of birth of the adopted child (if the child is under ten years old), and to include the adoptive parents (adoptive parent) in the child's birth certificate as the child's parents (parent)—if the adoptive parents (adoptive parent) wish to make the appropriate changes to the child's birth certificate⁶.

⁵ Доржиева С. В. СОХРАНЕНИЕ ТАЙНЫ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ (УДОЧЕРЕНИЯ) ДЕТЕЙ: ОБЫЧАИ НЕКОТОРЫХ НАРОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И СОВРЕМЕННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ //Вестник Бурятского государственного университета. Юриспруденция. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 26-32.

⁶ Юлдашева М. Б. Усыновление/удочерение-как оптимальная форма альтернативного обустройства детей //Здоровье как социокультурный феномен. – 2011. – С. 192-200.

The adoption application is signed by the adoptive parents (adopter). Other documents must also be attached to the application, such as a copy of the marriage certificate of the adoptive parents (adopter) - if the child is adopted by a married person (persons); a copy of the passport or identification ID card and a certificate that the adoptive parent is not married - if the child is adopted by a person who has never been married; a copy of the passport or identification ID card and a certificate that the adoptive parent is not married - if the child is adopted by a person who has never been married; a medical certificate on the state of health of the adoptive parents (adopter) (certificates from a psychiatric, tuberculosis and drug treatment institution, as well as an AIDS center); a certificate from the place of work of the adoptive parents (adopter) on the position held and salary, or a certificate of other sources of income; a document confirming the right of ownership of residential premises or the right to use residential premises and other documents provided for in Article 300 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Documents submitted by adoptive parents who are foreign citizens or stateless persons must be legalized or apostilled in accordance with the established procedure. These documents must be translated into the official language of the Republic of Uzbekistan and notarized. The documents specified in this article must be submitted to the court in duplicate. The court then prepares the cases for trial, and after the case is assigned, the cases are considered in accordance with Articles 301-302 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and a decision is then made in accordance with Article 303 of this Code⁷. The court is obliged, within three days from the date of entry into force of the adoption decision, to send a copy of this decision to the civil registry office at the place of birth registration of the adopted child.

Now let's look at the adoption procedure under English law. In England, adoption is regulated by the Adoption and Children Act 2002 (hereinafter referred to as the 2002 Act) and the Adoption Rules 2005 (hereinafter referred to as the 2005 Rules). According to Articles 50-51 of the Adoption and Children Act 2002, adoptive parents must be 21 years of age or older and have been permanently resident in a part of the British Isles for at least one year ending on the date of application (Article 49)⁸.

Adoption can be formalized by a married couple, but in some cases the law permits this only because one of the spouses is already the child's biological parent, and both individuals must be 18 years of age (clause "a" of Part Two of Article 50).

⁷ Доржиева С. В. СОХРАНЕНИЕ ТАЙНЫ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ (УДОЧЕРЕНИЯ) ДЕТЕЙ: ОБЫЧАИ НЕКОТОРЫХ НАРОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И СОВРЕМЕННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ //Вестник Бурятского государственного университета. Юриспруденция. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 26-32.

⁸ Татаринцева Е. А. Новые тенденции в развитии законодательства об усыновлении в Англии //Семейное и жилищное право. – 2009. – №. 4. – С. 14-16.

That is, if, for example:

- a woman (the child's mother) married a man who is not the child's father,
- then the husband can adopt his wife's child if he submits the application together with her,
- both husband and wife must be adults (18 years of age or older).

In other words, we are talking about the adoption of a child by one spouse of the other parent so that the child is legally recognized as their common property⁹.

The consent of a child is required if the child is 10 years of age or older and capable of understanding the meaning of adoption in accordance with Article 14 of the Adoption Regulations 2005. The consent of parents or persons with parental responsibility is required when placing a child for adoption – Article 19(1) of the 2002 Act. Consent may be overridden by a court if it is in the best interests of the child – Article 47 (Parts 2–7). The consent of the adoption agency is required when placing a child with prospective adoptive parents – Article 18 (Part 2). If the parents are deceased, unknown, or deprived of their parental rights, consent is not required – Article 47 (Parts 5–6). It is prohibited to bring a child to the UK for adoption without the permission of the competent authorities – Article 83 (Part 1). However, the Supreme Court may issue an order granting parental responsibility before adoption. Removing a child from the UK for adoption is permitted only with the permission of the court – Article 85 (Part 1) of the 2002 Act. The court is satisfied that the adoption abroad will comply with child protection principles and international obligations. According to Part 1, Chapter 3 of the Adoption and Children Act 2002 and the Adoption Regulations 2005, Article 14, an application for adoption is made to the Family Court or the High Court¹⁰.

British citizens who meet the established age and habitual residence requirements, and overseas nationals who have permission under section 83 of the Act, are eligible to apply. Before submitting an application, the child must have lived with the applicants for at least ten weeks, as provided for in section 42 (part 2) of the 2002 Act. In accordance with Part 1, Chapter 3 (sections 49–51) of the Adoption and Children Act 2002 and Regulations 14–15 of the Adoption Regulations 2005, the application (Form A58) must include the necessary information about the adoptive parents and the child being adopted¹¹. The application includes the personal information of the adoptive parents (surname, first name, date of birth, address, citizenship, marital status, and length of residence), as well as information about the child (name, date and place of birth, citizenship, place of residence, and

⁹ Татаринцева Е. А. Правовые последствия усыновления для ребенка по законодательству Российской Федерации, Англии и США // Право и политика. – 2012. – №. 1. – С. 68-78.

¹⁰ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2005/2795/made>

¹¹ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2005/2795/made>

the date of commencement of cohabitation with the applicants). Additionally, information about the biological parents or guardians, the grounds and motives for adoption, information about the adoption agency, and confirmation of the child's consent, if required by law, are provided¹². **In accordance with Rule 16 of the Adoption Regulations 2005, the following documents must be attached to an adoption application: the child's birth certificate, the adoptive parents' identity documents, medical reports, an adoption agency report, and written parental consent (Form A100, if applicable). The application must also include proof of the child's residence with the adoptive parents, issued by the local authority. In cases of international adoption, permissions relating to the child's entry or exit must be attached, in accordance with sections 83 to 85 of the Adoption and Children Act 2002¹³.**

Hearing of the case and making a decision. In accordance with Part 1, Chapter 4 of the Adoption and Children Act 2002, adoption cases are heard by the court in the manner prescribed by Articles 46–47 of this Act. During the trial, the court verifies the legality of the child's placement in a family as provided for in Article 19 of this Act, as well as the presence of consent from the parents, guardians, or adoption agency, or the existence of legal grounds for its absence in accordance with Article 47 of this Act. In addition, the court considers the adoption agency's report and takes into account the child's opinion if they are capable of expressing their will. When making a decision, the court is guided by the principle of the child's best interests, as enshrined in Article 1 of this Act. Adoption cases are heard in closed court, which is aimed at ensuring confidentiality and protecting the interests of the minor. In accordance with Part 1, Chapter 4, Articles 46–47 and 67 of the Adoption and Children Act 2002, if all the conditions stipulated by law are met, the court issues an adoption order (Article 46 (Part 1)). From the moment this order comes into force, the child legally acquires the status of the biological child of the adoptive parents, and all rights and obligations of the biological parents cease (Article 46 (Part 2)). In accordance with Article 67 (paragraphs 1–2) of the 2002 Act, new family legal relations are established between the adopted child and the adoptive parents, completely analogous to the relations between parents and biological children¹⁴. The court's decision is subject to registration in the Register of Adopted Children, after which the child is issued a new birth certificate reflecting the change in his or her family and legal status.

¹² Аботурова Ю. А. Проблемы международного усыновления // Научная перспектива. – 2017. – С. 20.

¹³ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>

¹⁴ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>

A comparative analysis of the legislation of England and the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that, despite the differences in legal systems—Anglo-Saxon in England and continental in Uzbekistan—both countries are focused on protecting the interests of the child during adoption.

In England, adoption is regulated by the Adoption and Children Act 2002. The decision to place a child with a family is made by the court based on a detailed report from the adoption agency¹⁵. The adoptive parents' living conditions, health, motivation, the child's opinion, and parental consent are all taken into account. All processes are conducted in closed sessions, and in international adoptions, the requirements of international law are additionally observed, including coordination with competent authorities and the child's entry regulations.

In Uzbekistan, adoption is conducted through the courts, with the mandatory participation of representatives of the guardianship and trusteeship authorities and the prosecutor. The process is regulated by the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Articles 151–172) and the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Articles 298–304). The consent of the parents and children over ten years of age is verified, and medical certificates, living conditions, and the socioeconomic capabilities of the adoptive parents are assessed. International adoption requires permission from the competent authority and legalization of documents. Uzbek law also thoroughly regulates the application form, the accompanying documents, and the procedure for amending a child's birth record.

Similarities between the two countries are evident in the basic requirements for adoptive parents: being of legal age, legally competent, having no criminal record for serious or dangerous crimes, and the mandatory consent of both parents and the child who has reached the required age. In both countries, adoption creates a new legal relationship between the child and the adoptive parents, terminates the rights of the biological parents, and provides for the possibility of annulment if the child's interests are violated.

Thus, although England and Uzbekistan have different legal systems and procedures, the key principles for protecting the rights and interests of a child during the adoption process are largely the same. This emphasizes that, despite national legislative differences, the goal of adoption remains the same: to provide a child with a safe and stable family environment.

REFERENCES

¹⁵ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>

1. Эсанова З. Н. Судебное рассмотрение дел об усыновлении в Узбекистане: дискуссии и предложения //Вестник Таджикского государственного университета права, бизнеса и политики. Серия гуманитарных наук. – 2009. – №. 1. – С. 33-40.
2. Шарахметова У. Защита прав несовершеннолетних детей в международном частном праве //Обзор законодательства Узбекистана. – 2018. – №. 2. – С. 83-85.
3. АТАЛЫКОВА Г. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДОСУДЕБНЫЙ ЭТАПА И ВОЗБУЖДЕНИЕ ДЕЛ ОБ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ РЕБЕНКА //“XXI АСРДА ИЛМ-ФАН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ ВА УЛАРДА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ” МАВЗУСИДАГИ РЕСПУБЛИКА ИЛМИЙ-ONLINE КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯСИ МАТЕРИАЛЛАРИ. – С. 40.
4. Латипова Н. М. ВОПРОСЫ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ ДЕТЕЙ, ОСТАВШИХСЯ БЕЗ ПОПЕЧЕНИЯ РОДИТЕЛЕЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН //Современная гуманитарная наука: проблемы и перспективы развития. – 2015. – С. 193-197.
5. Доржиева С. В. СОХРАНЕНИЕ ТАЙНЫ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ (УДОЧЕРЕНИЯ) ДЕТЕЙ: ОБЫЧАИ НЕКОТОРЫХ НАРОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И СОВРЕМЕННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ //Вестник Бурятского государственного университета. Юриспруденция. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 26-32.
6. Юлдашева М. Б. Усыновление/удочерение-как оптимальная форма альтернативного обустройства детей //Здоровье как социокультурный феномен. – 2011. – С. 192-200.
7. Эгамбердиев Э. Х. Актуальные проблемы семейного права Республики Узбекистан //ХАБАРШЫСЫ. – 2017. – С. 119.
8. Доржиева С. В. СОХРАНЕНИЕ ТАЙНЫ УСЫНОВЛЕНИЯ (УДОЧЕРЕНИЯ) ДЕТЕЙ: ОБЫЧАИ НЕКОТОРЫХ НАРОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ, И СОВРЕМЕННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ //Вестник Бурятского государственного университета. Юриспруденция. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 26-32.
9. Татаринцева Е. А. Новые тенденции в развитии законодательства об усыновлении в Англии //Семейное и жилищное право. – 2009. – №. 4. – С. 14-16.
10. Татаринцева Е. А. Правовые последствия усыновления для ребенка по законодательству Российской Федерации, Англии и США //Право и политика. – 2012. – №. 1. – С. 68-78.
11. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2005/2795/made>
12. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2005/2795/made>

13. Аботурова Ю. А. Проблемы международного усыновления // Научная перспектива. – 2017. – С. 20.
14. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>
15. Ивашкевич Е. Ф. Актуальные проблемы гражданства детей при международном усыновлении и разном гражданстве супругов. – 2019.
16. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>
17. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2002/38/enacted?view=interweave>

